

WOMEN'S ROLES IN PASTORAL SOCIETIES: RESPONSIBILITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

This research aimed to unpack the roles of pastoral women regarding their responsibilities and the challenges they face in their daily routine work. We focused on their lived experiences to gain insight into their perspective. We conducted qualitative research in the feminist tradition to cover the women's accounts about their daily routines in the interpretivist tradition. Thus, we interviewed 14 women with the help of purposive sampling technique. We conducted these interviews with women living across Mangla Garrison Society, Mangla, Pakistan. Our findings underscored a deeply embedded gender culture of inequalities in pastoral societies. We found that women play a central role to sustain daily routine life. However, they remained marginalized socially and economically. We also found that women are engaged in many tasks from dawn to dusk, i.e. herding, milking, cooking, and childcare. Despite this, their contribution is not valued mainly in decision making process. As the seasonal movement is concerned, it increases the women's burden at home while men move with herds. At longer distances. Similarly, women are central to livestock care and dairy production, they lack control over income, property rights, and resource access, reinforcing structural exclusion. Findings also showed how cultural norms restrict women's movement, limiting their access to communal resources, participation in public forums, and visibility in community decisions.

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1

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INTRODUCTION

Pastoral societies have been the subject of debate across societies (Onyima, 2021). Research shows that the gender division of labor is embedded in the cultural traditions and daily routine practices of pastoral communities (Adem, 2019). In pastoral societies, women play significant roles and share various responsibilities with men. These include herding small livestock of goats and sheep, milking animals, processing dairy products, collecting water and firewood, and managing household chores. Eneyew and Mengistu (2013) found that women often take care of children and elders, coupled with preparing food and maintaining the house. Men primarily take responsibility for managing large herds of cattle, including herds, horses and sheep. They are also involved in herds over long distances, engage in market issues, and handle external negotiations. Wangui (2014) argued that division of labor is both physical expectations and traditional roles and norms. All the responsibilities are subject to seasonal variations. Men spend most of

1

their time with their herds, while women work inside and deal with domestic chores. Women are sometimes required to assume some additional agricultural or resource duties. Similarly, Flintan (2008) asserted that women may contribute to livestock management. Although women have a central role in sustaining pastoral livelihoods, their work is often undermined and devalued. Likewise, their contribution is also overlooked in managing formal economic assessment and decision-making processes.

Women have a key role that is often unrecognized to sustain the household economy, including livestock care, dairy production, and small-scale trade, forming the backbone of pastoral livelihood (Karmebäck, Wairore, Jirström, & Nyberg, 2015). They are also responsible for managing small livestock of goats and sheep, feeding and watering animals, and ensuring their health. Besides, Yurco (2024) oversaw the milking and processing of dairy products, of butter, cheese, and yogurt, that are consumed either by family members or sold in the local market. This helps them to generate revenue from their products. In addition, women are also engaged in small-scale trade of selling milk, handicrafts, and other items while contributing to their household income and food security. Despite significant labor, Wangui (2003) uncovered that women's control over income and resources remained limited owing to the patriarchal norms. All the income heads are under the control of men's household heads, limiting the women's financial autonomy and undermining decision-making processes. Similarly, Graham (2002) contended that the right to inheritance and property is restricted by men, showing them merely as the caretakers.

In nomadic societies, the mobility of women is steered by the demands of daily life as well as sociocultural constraints. Wangui (2008) argued that mobility is important for women, like men, to move in search of grazing land with water. However, women's mobility is limited to some socio-cultural boundaries. Although they move in groups during the seasonal migration, but remain limited to the household duties, childcare, while managing the domestic chores. Verma and Khadka (2016) found that their mobility is often governed by sociocultural expectations that defined their behaviors. It is noteworthy that sociocultural norms often place significant restrictions on the mobility of women. Spencer (1998) stated that concerns of honor and safety often prevented women from traveling and participating in economic and social activities. Such restrictions reduced their access to markets, education, healthcare, and decision-making within and outside the home. Bhasin (2011) explained that females are required to have permission from men to leave home or visit distant areas for any purpose.

Maeda-Machang et al. (1986) found that pastoralists do not have communal access to the resources of water and grazing land. They further stated that communal access to resources is also a gendered concept where men tend to have control over these spaces, while women's access is a secondary issue. Hodgson (1999) shows that men regulate authority. This affects the abilities of women to contribute to their livestock management and their reduced mobility in community engagement. This further shows how gender inequalities are perpetuated and constrain women's potential in subsistence economies.

Women play a key role as caregivers while bearing responsibilities to maintain family health (Galwab, Koech, Wasonga, & Kironchi, 2024). Such roles are deeply associated with the challenges that women face in remote and resource-scarce environments. Here, access to maternal health services is either denied or limited due to the geographic location of these communities. They face severe health infrastructure issues where no trained medical staff is available. These women travel long distances on foot or unreliable transport to access the nearby health facility. This shows either delay or denial of access to antenatal care.

Women primary caregivers take care of children, the elderly, and sick people. They are always with less external support and low access to resources. Dahl (1987) stated that women's responsibilities increase during seasonal migration or in some crisis, bringing some physical and emotional strains to their health. Despite a key role in the migration process, their health in general and reproductive health in particular is affected and neglected within families. Wangui (2003) added that the lack of health infrastructure further exacerbates these challenges. Yurco (2024) added that cultural barriers and gendered norms also restricted women's abilities to seek care.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The gender division of labor of pastoral societies is often reflected in cultural norms. While women perform a wide range of responsibilities, their contribution is never valued. In these societies, women are

often responsible for milking animals, processing dairy products, collecting water and firewood, and managing household duties (Adem, 2019; Dahl, 1987). Such responsibilities are important to the survival of the households, particularly in a semi-arid and migratory context. On the contrary, men normally oversee larger livestock and undertake tasks of mobility, moving at long distances with herds coupled with market-related issues (Onyima, 2021). Flintan (2008) said that the roles of men are visible and recognized than women in the economy and structure, while women's roles remain informal with secondary importance often overlooked by men. Moreover, seasonal variations also affect the division of labor by shaping labor. Eneyew and Mengistu (2013) stated that during migration or dry seasons, women's workload increases as men travel with herds while leaving women behind to manage domestic chores and agricultural activities. Despite their central roles in pastoral economies, the labor of women is rarely valued and accounted for in economic assessment and development planning (Yurco, 2024). Kipuri and Ridgewell (2008) said that recognized and documented gendered patterns are important to create equitable policies and support systems against the unique needs and contributions of pastoral women.

Research shows that women in pastoral societies make a significant contribution to the pastoral economy through livestock care, dairy products, and small-scale trade, while their roles are often devalued and they are often found invisible in the formal economy (Onyango, 2023). While women are essentially responsible for managing the small livestock, milk animals, and processing dairy products for family consumption and sale that generate income (Onyima, 2021; Gurmu, 2018). Research further shows that women are also engaged in the formal trade of selling milk, butter, or home-made goods. These goods contribute to household food security, bringing financial stability (Gizaw et al., 2021). Nonetheless, despite their labor, they are consistently losing control over income and assets because financial decision-making is often in the hands of men (Davis et al., 2012). Yurco (2024) argued that ownership and inheritance of livestock are also gendered, as economic resources are similarly transcended on a typical male lineage that further limits women's economic agency and security. It is noted that women who care for their animals are rarely recognized as owners. Such systematic inequalities restricted women's access to credit, decision-making, and resource development. Glass (2019) analyzed that gender sensitive policies can bring legal reforms to essentialize the roles of women in pastoral economies to improve the sustainability of pastoralism.

Wulifan, Dordah, and Sumankuuro (2022) argued that the mobility of women is shaped by the demands of the environment and restricted gender roles. The pastoral livelihood requires movement while searching the grazing lands and water. Here, women's mobility is often confined to domestic chores and camp-based activities. This shows that women have no broader communal and economic engagement (Flintan, 2008). The sociocultural norms of being modest, honor, and gendered roles restricted women from traveling or accompanying, or accessing public space freely (Vijayalakshmy et al., 2023). Such restrictions reduce women's visibility in resource management and weaken them in the decision-making process, though they play a key role in fetching water, collecting firewood, and caring for livestock at home (Glass, 2019). Likewise, the communal grazing lands are possessed and accessed by men, while women's contribution is not recognized despite having sufficient participation (Jebena et al., 2022). Such spatial limitations constrained women's contribution to pastoral economies and hindered their access to education, health, and the market. Ayele (2019) emphasized the gender sensitive interventions that promote the mobility of women and recognize their right to the resources.

Women's health, including reproductive health, is linked with their duties as primary caregivers; however, they face significant challenges in accessing essential health services. The remoteness of pastoral regions, maternal healthcare, including antenatal care, birth attendance, and emergency services, is often out of reach (Walker et al., 2022; Schelling et al., 2016). This led to high risks of maternal and infant mortality, while sociocultural norms also limit women's access because male permission is important to seek care and avoid services due to stigmas attached with male healthcare providers (Flintan, 2008). Normally, women tended to children, the elderly, and the sick, often without any proper medical training (Graham, 2002). This burden increases during seasonal migration or some crises that affect both their physical and mental well-being. Bhasin (2011) stated that limiting health infrastructure, lack of healthcare facilities, staffing, and

medicine worsened the situation when it comes to women's health. Such systematic barriers reflect gender inequalities in pastoral communities.

METHODOLOGY

We conducted this study with pastoral families living across the Mangla Garrison Society Mangla. We explored the women's roles by listening and recording their lived experiences. We intend to know the challenges and responsibilities they have in their families when their men set out with herds on high altitudes. We employed qualitative research design and used interpretive research method to know their lived experiences.

We found pastoral families living across the Mangla Garrison Housing Society. We contacted them through a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) that worked on their capacity building. After their consent, we were allowed to interview the women at home. There were almost 10 families where more than 20 women were living with their children. We took almost two months to interview women. Thus, a sample of 14 women was interviewed with the help of purposive sampling technique.

A semi-structured interview guide was designed with careful considerations to interview the women in pastoral societies. It allowed participants to feel free while sharing their experiences. The study focused on the key areas of their division of labor, movement, economy, resources, and health care challenges they face. We listened to their accounts of role taking. The interviews were conducted in the local language because they do not even know Urdu. Thus, one of the researchers knew their language. The interviews were recorded with the consent of the participants. Notes were also taken by us.

We employed thematic analysis of Braun and Clarke (2006) and analyzed the collected data. We transcribed data manually by comparison process. We used six steps to identify the themes from sub-themes. We identified four key themes, i.e. gender division of labor, economic contribution, mobility restriction, and healthcare challenges.

We took informed consent from the participants at two stages. First, we contacted the families and got consent to do research while we obtained consent of each participant in the study. We kept their names and identities confidential. They were given pseudonymous as P-1-14. All the information provided by the participants was kept confidential and safe as per the research ethics.

KEY FINDINGS

The following themes were extracted and interpreted.

Table 1 Themes and sub-themes of the study.

Gendered Division of Labor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily tasks and responsibilities of women (herding, milking, household management) • Comparison with men's roles • Seasonal variations in labor
Economic Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women's role in livestock care, dairy production, and small-scale trade • Control over income or resources • Access to livestock ownership and inheritance rights
Mobility and Spatial Boundaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women's mobility in nomadic or semi-nomadic contexts • Social norms limiting movement • Access to communal grazing land or water sources
Health and Reproductive Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to maternal health services • Women's roles as caregivers • Impact of limited health infrastructure in remote areas

Gendered Division of Labor

The gendered division of labor has a central role in the daily routine of women who undertake various essential roles at the same time; However, their roles are always devalued. As Hodgson (2000) noted that pastoral women are the hidden backbone of the pastoral communities. This theme revealed how routine

duties structure the gender lines, where women are taking on many tasks and roles at the same time. As one of the participants stated, "From dawn to dusk, I have to work, milking animals, feeding children, fetching water, and cooking. This wide range of work never ends." Another added, "My morning starts with work and ends working when I go to sleep is the only rest area, we women often find, unfortunately." This shows that the nature of labor carried out by women encompassed herding small livestock, dairy products, and household management. On the contrary, men work outside and have the mobility to move for the completion of various tasks. A respondent said, "My duty begins with the cattle, I take them to grazing while I have to take care of the home as well." This excerpt shows the cultural embedded perception that females are not productive in economic activities. In this way, their participation and contribution are less valued.

Movement of pastorals in the summer season is also one major reason that shape labor dynamics among women. During this time, men move on longer distances with herds at high altitude while females remain at homes and work from dawn to dusk to meet the familial responsibilities. A woman shared her experience, "Men leave home with cattle, and I have to take care of the entire home, including children, animals, and elderly persons. It consumes most of the time and energy." This highlighted the nexus of gender and seasonal labor that increases the labor for women for their livelihood survival.

Based on the above data, it is concluded that household survival is on the verge of women's labor. Although women are often invisible in decision-making and other structures. Thus, it reinforces gender inequalities in pastoral lives.

Economic Contributions

The second theme of the study highlighted the women's roles that are essential but often overlooked to sustain the household economy. The study findings revealed that women are engaged in domestic, livestock, and dairy production. One woman said, "Dailly, I milk animals and make the dairy products that we sell in the market and generate some money that is consumed to meet many ends of daily life." The majority of the women agreed that "money goes to their husbands while they just produce the items to make money." This reflected one of the common patterns where women significantly contributed to the production and trade, but they lacked control over the resources and hence the income they produced. Despite labor, they remain outside the decision-making realms of power and money while men dominate.

Women involved in the local trade of selling milk or manmade products and goods are evidence of their contribution. A woman stated, "I cannot buy anything I wish because I have to take special approval to buy and a stronger justification for the usage." This excerpt shows that women experience extremely restricted autonomy owing to the patriarchal structure of society. Here, access to livestock ownership and inheritance is another important concern. One woman stated, "I do not own anything; everything is owned by my brothers or husband. I am just a care provider." This excerpt highlighted the systematic exclusion of women from economic rights despite women's daily contributions to the work.

The above findings enable us to argue that women's labor and economic agencies have an intersection of what women need to be part of decision-making and role-taking. This may recognize the strength of women's roles in pastoral societies.

Mobility and Spatial Boundaries

The third theme of study revealed how women's mobility is shaped and restrained by cultural norms and environmental conditions. The participants commonly expressed limited mobility despite living in mobile communities. As one participant stated, "The animals move with men at longer distances. We cannot move away from camps. To move, we need men accompanied lest we remain bound to home." It shows that gender norms restrict females to move and have access to public and economic resources while we see movement a key element to the survival in these pastoral communities.

Like other traditional societies, women are under the influence of patriarchal sociocultural expectations of honor and modesty that limit their mobility. Similarly, their modesty is expected in their retrained home-based activities. One woman remarked, "Social norms force us to stay at home and stick to our traditions and customs. Women at home are honored while females working outside, even brining water, are talked about Such restrictions reduce abilities of women to have access to the communal grazing land,

water sources, and cottage industry. Another participant said, “I see men can attend the gathering in families or resources while women stay at homes and follow the directions by men.” It indicates that how spatial boundaries reinforce exclusion of females from sociocultural processes related access to resources. It is pertinent to mention here that women contribute to various tasks of such as watering animals, collecting fodder, which fall within the narrow-defined zones. Based on above results, we found that female mobility is more political than physical. It reflects main gender inequalities that constrained female agency and their visibility in pastoral communities.

Health and Reproductive Roles

The last theme of the study highlighted the barriers faced by women due to the lack of access and the burden of caregiving. It is revealed that women lack access to maternal health services. One participant shared, “We normally give birth to a child at home without any help because hospitals are far away and there are few facilities.” This shows that distance, poor infrastructure, and lack of transport have highly restricted access to skilled birth care.

Findings also revealed that women are primary caregivers in many households. They are also responsible for the healthcare of children, the elderly, as well as the sick. A woman stated, “In my family, if someone falls ill, it is my responsibility to take care, even in conditions when I am unwell.” This double burden is unnoticed and remains unaddressed in health planning. Another woman added, “In case of a serious issue, we go to the healthcare center. I see there are no doctors, while medicines are also scarce.” These excerpts reflected the intertwined intersection between gender, geography, and structural neglect of women. We assert that health of females is neglected the most as they are expected to be taken care of. This indicates how there is an urgent need to improve the rural health structure and provide services to the women from pastoral communities.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the deeply embedded gender inequalities in pastoral societies, where women play critical roles in sustaining daily life, yet remain socially and economically marginalized. The gendered division of labor revealed that women engaged in a wide array of labor herding, milking, cooking, and childcare, yet their work is culturally devalued and largely invisible in decision-making structures. Seasonal variations intensify this burden, as men migrate with herds and women are left managing households alone. Similarly, the theme of economic contributions highlighted that while women are central to livestock care and dairy production, they lack control over income, property rights, and resource access, reinforcing structural exclusion. Findings also showed how cultural norms restrict women’s movement, limiting their access to communal resources, participation in public forums, and visibility in community decisions. Finally, the inadequate rural healthcare system is exposed, where women are not provided access, coupled with caregiving responsibilities, compromising their own well-being. Overall, the data illustrates that pastoral women's labor is foundational to household survival, yet their contributions are overlooked and undervalued. Addressing these gendered disparities requires inclusive policy interventions that recognize women's roles, enhance their autonomy, and improve access to healthcare, economic resources, and decision-making spaces

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